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VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

CYTOTOXIC LESION OF THE CORPUS CALLOSUM IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT: CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

The corpus callosum is the primary commissural area formed by white matter tracts that provides interhemispheric communication between the two cerebral hemispheres.

In recent years, cytotoxic lesions observed in the splenium of the corpus callosum have been identified by Magnetic Resonance imaging (MRI). These lesions which are called cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum, are rare radiological findings that can be seen secondary to a wide range of diseases.

We present a case of a patient presenting to the Emergency Department with left leg pain and numbness on the left side of the face, who had a cytotoxic lesion of the corpus callosum

Case: *A 31-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department with complaints of pain in his left leg and numbness in the left side of his face. The physical examination is normal. Vital signs are normal. The patient's diffusion MRI showed a cytotoxic lesion of the corpus callosum as a well-defined, oval lesion with hyperintense diffusion restriction in the central part of the corpus callosum, corresponding to a hypointense lesion on ADC. The patient was admitted to the neurology clinic for follow-up*

Discussion and conclusion *Cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum are secondary lesions associated with drug therapy, malignancies, infections, subarachnoid hemorrhage, metabolic diseases, head trauma, and more recently, Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) Cases are usually asymptomatic, but may present with symptoms such as headache, confusion, seizures, and delirium. Although cerebrovascular disease is primarily considered when interpreting imaging in patients presenting to the emergency department with neurological complaints, cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum should be kept in mind, too*

KEYWORDS; *Corpus Callosum, numbness, emergency service, magnetic resonance (MR), cytotoxic lesion*

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INTRODUCTION

The corpus callosum is the primary commissural area formed by white matter tracts that provides interhemispheric communication between the two cerebral hemispheres(1). Anatomically, the corpus callosum is divided into four distinct parts: rostrum, genu, body, and splenium. These components connect the corresponding centers of the right and left cerebral hemispheres and provide comprehensive neural coordination.(1)

In recent years, cytotoxic lesions observed in the splenium of the corpus callosum have been identified by Magnetic Resonance imaging (MRI). These lesions which are called cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum, are rare radiological findings that can be seen secondary to a wide range of diseases.(3)

We present a case of a patient presenting to the Emergency Department with left leg pain and numbness on the left side of the face, who had a cytotoxic lesion of the corpus callosum. When interpreting MRI images in patients presenting to the emergency department with neurological complaints, cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum should also be considered.

CASE REPORT

A 31-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department with complaints of pain in his left leg and numbness in the left side of his face. He was routinely taking hydroxychloroquine, which had been initiated by the rheumatology department. Patient's vital signs: blood pressure 120/60 mmHg, pulse 80 beats/min, oxygen saturation 98%, temperature 36.6°C.

Neurological examination of the patient revealed a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15, the patient was conscious, cooperative, oriented, and had bilateral positive light reflexes. There was no nuchal rigidity. Muscle strength was 5/5 in the upper extremities and 5/5 in the lower extremities. The patient's vision and hearing were normal. The patient's facial nerve examination was normal. Speech was normal. The patient only reported numbness on the left side of his face.

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The patient's pulses were palpable in the extremities, but there was no discoloration. There was no difference in circumference in the lower extremities. The patient's other system examinations were normal. The patient's complete blood count and routine biochemistry tests were normal.

A computed tomography (CT) scan of the brain was performed to explain the patient's complaints. No pathology was detected on the CT scan. A diffusion brain MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) scan was requested for the patient.

The patient's diffusion MRI showed a cytotoxic lesion of the corpus callosum as a well-defined, oval lesion with hyperintense diffusion restriction in the central part of the corpus callosum, corresponding to a hypointense lesion on ADC (Figures 1, 2). We consulted with the neurology clinic. The patient was admitted to the neurology clinic for follow-up. Symptomatic treatment was provided at the neurology clinic. During two days of observation, the patient's symptoms completely resolved. Since no new pathology was detected in the patient's follow-up imaging, the patient was discharged.

Figure 1.Hyperintense oval, well-defined lesion in the corpus callosum

Figure 2. Hyperintense lesion's hypointense counterpart in the ADC

DISCUSSION

Cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum are secondary lesions associated with drug therapy, malignancies, infections (adenovirus, aseptic meningitis or encephalitis, Epstein-Barr virus, Escherichia coli, herpes, influenza virus A, influenza, Legionella, malaria, measles, Mycoplasma, mumps, rotavirus, Salmonella, Staphylococci, Streptococci, tick-borne encephalitis, varicella-zoster virus), subarachnoid hemorrhage, metabolic diseases, head trauma, and more recently, Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).(3,4,5,6).

Cases are usually asymptomatic, but may present with symptoms such as headache, confusion, seizures, and delirium.(8) Our patient presented with symptoms of leg pain and facial numbness. In their series of four cases, Büyükşerbetçi et al. reported patient complaints including fever, blurred vision, fatigue, headache, tinnitus, focal seizures, and confusion.(1) In the case presented by Durmuş et al., it was reported as temporary vision loss.(7) In a series of studies, Barbuoğlu et al. identified neurological symptoms such as dysarthria, altered consciousness, ataxia, syncope, epileptic seizures, and headache. (8) In the same study, it was determined that lesions developed due

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to the direct or indirect effect of various infections on the central nervous system as an etiological factor. The study also identified metabolite decompression due to uremia in diabetic patients, subarachnoid hemorrhage, asthma attacks, trauma, high-dose lithium-levetiracetam intake, and anti-epileptic drug interactions.(8) We were unable to identify the etiological factor in our case.

CONCLUSION

Although cerebrovascular disease is primarily considered when interpreting imaging in patients presenting to the emergency department with neurological complaints, cytotoxic lesions of the corpus callosum should be kept in mind when the emergency physician detects a well-defined, oval lesion showing T2 hyperintense and diffusion restriction in the central part of the corpus callosum.

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